

FORMAL VERSUS INFORMAL FIRMS PERFORMANCES: THE CASE OF VIETNAMESE ENTERPRISES

Marco Di Cintio¹

Abstract: *This paper aims to analyze the different performances of formal vs. informal firms in terms of R&D, Innovation, and Productivity. Using data from the 2011, 2013, and 2015 results of the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprise Survey in Vietnam, we also evaluate the effects of the transition from an informal to a formal status on firms' innovativeness and productivity. After accounting for the under-reporting of R&D investments of informal establishments, we show that (i) informal firms invest less in R&D and (ii) those who switch to a formal status have a higher probability of introducing innovations. However, even though formal firms are more likely to introduce radical or soft innovations, our results also reveal that (iii) – against all odds – the 'underdog' informal Vietnamese firms show a higher level of productivity when they are able to innovate. These findings also hold when we control for a reverse causality effect of firms' productivity that may result in a driven factor of their formalizations.*

Keywords: *Informal firms; Innovation; Productivity; R&D; Vietnam.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The informal economy is an abstract concept that permeates many sectors and levels of activity and encompasses a heterogeneous group of actors. Informality is a term used to describe the collection of firms, workers and activities taking place below the government radar. However, there is still no consensus regarding the definition of the informal economy, and different expressions – almost indiscriminately – refer to this phenomenon. The most commonly used terms include underground, shadows or unofficial economy, but also, informal sector and informal or hidden activity. Dabla-Norris *et al.* (2008) conceptualize informal economic activity as contributing to gross domestic product but not currently reported. The definition provid-

¹ Dipartimento di Scienze dell'Economia, University of Salento, Lecce, Italy.

ed by Perry *et al.* (2007) characterizes informal firms and workers as those who operate at the fringes of applicable laws and regulations. Nevertheless, the term informality excludes all kinds of activities explicitly considered illegal. Hence, informal (legal) economic activities may take many forms, such as the unregistered small firms, the street vendors, and the large registered formal firms that employ a share of their workers without offering them written contracts, access to social benefits, and unemployment protections.

According to these definitions, the informal economy includes both informal jobs and firms. Both informal jobs and informal firms play a significant role in many economies worldwide. The literature recognizes that the informal sector plays a significant role in the economy of developing countries. It contributes around 35% to the gross domestic product (Loayza, 2016) and employs a large portion of the population, particularly in urban areas (Nguimkeu, 2014). Informal businesses often have lower barriers to entry than formal businesses, which makes them an important source of livelihood for many people (La Porta & Shleifer, 2008). This is particularly true in Africa where the informal sector is more prominent and noticeable. Indeed, a substantial portion of non-agricultural jobs, between 30-90%, are in the informal sector (African Development Bank, 2018). It represents about 70% of jobs (African Development Bank, 2018) and between 20-65% of GDP (International Monetary Fund, 2017). Moreover, India has approximately 1.6 million registered enterprises, compared to 26 million unregistered firms (Kushnir *et al.*, 2010). However, informality is a pervasive phenomenon all over the world. It accounts for 10 to 20% of GDP in most OECD countries, 20 to 30% in Southern European OECD countries and Central European transition economies (Schneider & Enste 2000). Throughout the world, two-thirds of all enterprises are unregistered at their start-up (Autio & Fu, 2015) and over half of all current enterprises operate without registering (Acs *et al.*, 2013).

The nature of informal activity generally depends on the level of the country's development. However, in emerging countries, informal activity refers mostly to tax evasion and the use of undeclared labor. In emerging economies, informal activity is the source of employment for a significant share of the labor force, often making up for the weak potential of the formal sector to create enough jobs. The underdevelopment of the formal private sector may stem from a variety of causes, from inefficient bureaucracies to low levels of human capital and low trust in public institutions.

Emerging economies usually face an environment of stringent regulation, unreliable institutions, and low productivity, where informality is the only possibility for a large fraction of the population. In such cases, attempts to reduce informality may destroy informal jobs and might lead to even worse outcomes in terms of economic growth. Entrepreneurship, both formal and informal, is heavily influenced by governance quality. Earlier research has demonstrated that good governance creates an enabling environment for individuals to introduce innovative products or services. Indeed, as indicated by Baumol (1990), good governance plays a prominent role in determining the distribution of different types of entrepreneurship. Furthermore, Klapper *et al.* (2009) argue that improved regulation encourages firms to operate in the formal sector.

Moreover, entrepreneurs' abilities are among the key factors of economic and social change that led to an increase in formal entrepreneurship. For instance, Ali *et al.* (2019) remark that robust legal frameworks, transparent registration processes, and favorable economic and political governance have a positive correlation with the rates of formal entrepreneurship at the national level. Therefore, the transition from an informal economy to a formal one can have positive effects on various levels. Formal enterprises tend to outperform informal ones in terms of their survival rate, size, and growth. Informal firms are often situated in underdeveloped locations with limited economic and physical infrastructure, relying on labor-intensive pro-

ductions and outdated machinery. They also tend to employ workers with lower education and skill levels.

At the macro level, a larger number of formal enterprises has a positive impact on GDP level and its growth rate. It implies that countries with larger formal economies tend to have higher levels of GDP per capita, as supported by La Porta and Shleifer (2008). In addition, a transition towards a larger formal economy would result in benefits for many employees. Formal employees generally receive higher wages than informal employees, which can be attributed to their higher labor productivity. Furthermore, working conditions are comparatively better and well-protected in formal enterprises than in informal ones. Another advantage of increasing the number of formal enterprises is that it would lead to a corresponding rise in public taxes, which could be utilized for various national socio-economic programs. The transition from an informal to a formal economy also has the potential to enhance the public perception of government quality, which could lead to a positive impact on the willingness to adhere to regulations (De Mel *et al.*, 2013). Nonetheless, there is potential for these factors to mutually reinforce each other. On the one hand, higher tax revenues from formal businesses enable greater public investment in infrastructure and education, which can lead to improved workforce skills and competencies. On the other hand, better working conditions and high-skilled workers can increase firms' productivity by incentivizing their formalization.

In this context, our study extends previous research along two dimensions. First, our study integrates both R&D investments and innovation outcomes into an empirical model of firms' productivity in the context of developing countries with both formal and informal firms. This, to the best of our knowledge, has not been studied in the earlier literature. Indeed, the new richness of the data on firms' innovation activities in emerging countries allowed us to implement the *Crépon-Duguet-Mairesse* (CDM) structural model (Crépon *et al.*, 1998), in which firm productivity is a function of *radical* or *soft* innovations, which in

turn are explained by the R&D intensity of firms. Our second contribution is related to the attention we give to the informal status of Vietnamese enterprises in the specific context of innovative firms. From this standpoint, the lack of data and difficulties in measuring innovations have limited the empirical research on the connection between innovations and firm productivity in developing countries, especially with respect to informal firms. Thus, our paper tries to fill this gap. By using data from the 2011, 2013, and 2015 results of the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprise Survey in Vietnam, we build a three-stage empirical model, where (i) we account for the under-reporting of R&D in informal establishments; (ii) estimate the innovation likelihood of firms due to R&D and to the *switch to a formal status*; and (iii) evaluate the simultaneous effects of both innovations and the *transition from an informal to a formal status* on firms' productivity, shedding light on labor productivity differences between formal and informal firms.

Accounting for a potential endogeneity, we show that: (i) informal firms invest less in R&D and (ii) those who *switch to a formal status* have a higher probability of introducing innovations. However, while we find that formal firms are more likely to introduce innovations, our results also reveal that (iii) – against all odds – the '*underdog*' informal Vietnamese firms show a higher level of productivity when they are able to innovate. Overall, the empirical evidence in our study suggests policy interventions aimed at stimulating the transition of firms from an informal to a formal status. In practice, benefits may be expected from policies that promote a business research environment where informal firms grow as successful innovators. Moreover, since innovative informal firms are found to be more productive than formal ones, greater economic advantages can be expected in terms of within-firm human capital growth and knowledge development by encouraging informal firms to operate in the formal sector but leaving them to maintain their high level of flexibility.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the determinants and consequences of informal activities

under the lens of the main four theories on informality, as well as the policy interventions aimed at reducing informality (Section 2.1). Moreover, we concentrate our attention on the different performances that informal firms, compared to formal firms, may have in terms of R&D, Innovation and Productivity (Section 2.2). Section 3 describes our research methodology. Data used in the study is described in section 4 and section 5 discusses the empirical results. Section 6 concludes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, we review the economic literature on the determinants and consequences of informal activities. Specifically, Section 2.1 provides the theoretical and empirical background behind the main theories on informality, which are not all necessarily focused on firms' R&D, Innovation and Productivity. In addition, we discuss the specific context of innovative (formal vs. informal) firms in Section 2.2.

2.1. Literature background on informality

Even though the literature on the economics of informality is deep and diverse, it can be divided into two basic strands, according to the trade-offs generated by the informal sector. The public finance perspective emphasizes the trade-off between taxes and public services. Thus, informal firms avoid some fees and taxes at the cost of reduced access to public services (Loayza, 1996; Johnson *et al.*, 1998; Ihrig & Moe, 2004; Prado, 2011; D'Erasmus & Moscoso Boedo, 2012). The other strand of literature takes a labor perspective, focusing on the trade-off between labor and capital costs. Hence, in this perspective, informal firms avoid some mandated labor costs (such as minimum wages, benefits and firing constraints) at the expense of higher capital costs. In particular, the labor market perspective focuses on informal employment, studies its determinants and often pays particular attention to the wage and income differences between formal and informal sectors. Indeed, the renewed attention to the informal

economy led policymakers to implement policies that aim at tackling both informal firms and informal employment (Ulyssea, 2018). However, the factors driving the formalization of these two components are distinct and require separate examination. This review specifically concentrates on informal firms rather than informal employment. Therefore, we briefly outline the key four theoretical perspectives on informal firms as they drive different policy interventions.

Besides theoretical contributions that attempt to explain the reasons for and consequences of firms' informality, the literature also views informality as something that may have to be lived with for a while, but which it would be better to eliminate. Not surprisingly, the strategies for reducing informality are often at the top of policymakers' priorities. Indeed, many economists noticed that informality is likely to appear as one of the most difficult challenges facing developing countries. In this regard, governments and policymakers promote formalization through various interventions ranging from the simplification of registration procedures to increased law enforcement. These interventions can be categorized into three main policy approaches: (a) cutting costs and simplifying procedures of formalization, (b) increasing its benefits, and (c) increasing both the level of enforcement and firm inspections by public officers.

Very often, informality offers the benefits of avoiding the burden of regulation and taxation. However, by operating outside the formal and regulatory framework, agents suffer the costs of not having the protection and services that the law and the State can provide. Therefore, informality is sometimes the outcome of agents being '*excluded*' from formality as this involves high costs of registration and long bureaucratic procedures. Under a different context, it is the result of agents '*exiting*' the formal sector as a consequence of cost-benefit considerations. In contrast, two other competing models argue that informal firms have a '*deleterious*' effect on economic growth or, alternatively, that informal and formal firms operate in two distinct '*dualistic*' spheres without reciprocal spillover effects. Hence, four main

models dominate the theoretical literature concerning the decision of formalizing or not a business: (I) the *exclusion model* (De Soto, 1990 and 2003), (II) the *rational exit model* (Maloney, 2004), (III) the *parasite model* (Baily *et al.*, 2006; Farrell, 2004 and 2006 Furthermore), and (IV) the *dual economy model* (La Porta & Shleifer, 2008 and 2014).

The *exclusion model* states that formalizing a business is difficult for some firms due to high costs and long bureaucratic processes, resulting in their exclusion from the formal economy (De Soto, 2003 and 1990). This model suggests that policy intervention to promote formalization should focus on reducing costs and streamlining the process of formalizing a business. Such an approach has had a significant impact on policymakers, including the World Bank, which has advocated for regulatory reforms aimed at making it easier and faster for businesses to formalize (La Porta & Shleifer, 2014; Bruhn & Mc Kenzie, 2013). These policies, however, may have limited effects (Campos *et al.*, 2015; De Andrade *et al.*, 2014). Even though these policies may increase the number of registered firms, it could be mainly attributable to the creation of new formal enterprises rather than to the switching of existing informal firms (Bruhn, 2011; Klapper *et al.*, 2006).

The *exit model* (Perry, 2007; Maloney, 2004), in contrast to the exclusion model, takes into account both the costs and benefits of formalizing a business. According to this model, firms weigh the costs and benefits of formalization and decide to formalize only when the benefits are greater than the costs. In this case, policymakers can encourage formalization by reducing the costs and/or increasing the benefits of registering a business, such as development services, tax exemptions and credit facilities.

In sharp contrast to the exclusion and exit models, the *parasite model* suggests that informal enterprises hinder economic growth as they evade some taxes and compete unfairly with formal firms by avoiding the cost of formalization (Baily *et al.*, 2006; Farrell, 2006 and 2004). This model sees the choice of formality as influenced by the

quality of regulation and enforcement. When there is weak enforcement and high costs for formalizing, firms operate informally. Interventions that increase enforcement - such as awareness campaigns about the legal risks of informality or more frequent official inspections - are necessary to address this specific context.

Finally, the *dual economy model* (La Porta & Shleifer, 2014 and 2008) proposes that formal and informal enterprises operate in separate spheres and that informal firms do not hinder the growth of formal ones. According to this model, informal firms are typically small, use limited external finance, and are low-skilled and less productive compared to formal enterprises. Most informal enterprises are engaged in unproductive activities that are expected to disappear as highly productive formal enterprises grow and drive economic development. Thus, the dual economy model argues that there is no need for specific policy interventions aimed at promoting the formalization of informal firms, as they are considered to be unresponsive. Regulatory reforms that make the formalization easier may be however beneficial for the whole economy.

As a matter of fact, formalization is thought to bring about positive outcomes for the economy, such as increased economic growth, job creation, higher labor productivity, better labor conditions, and improved social protection (Tijdens *et al.*, 2015; Gatti *et al.*, 2014). On the other hand, informal firms are seen as harmful to the economy as they tend to underreport employment, evade taxes, and harm formal firms by not paying regulatory costs or respecting copyrights (Schneider *et al.*, 2011; Farrell, 2008 and 2004; Baily *et al.*, 2006). Therefore, governments and policymakers have recently placed a greater emphasis on addressing the informal economy, as evidenced by its inclusion in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

As already discussed, there is a wide range of policies aimed at promoting formalization (Williams & Round, 2007). These formalization policies may also involve improving access to credit, providing training, and other business support services for informal activities.

However, despite numerous attempts by policymakers to bring the informal economy into the formal sector, there is still a lack of systematic evidence on the impact of these formalization efforts. There is limited knowledge about how firms respond to formalization policies and interventions, and the available literature provides conflicting evidence of their effectiveness (Bruhn & McKenzie, 2014). The majority of micro-level studies examine the impact of regulatory reforms aimed at reducing financial and time costs (Goldszmidt *et al.*, 2018; Rocha *et al.*, 2018; Rothenberg *et al.*, 2015; Aparicio, 2014; Bruhn, 2013 and 2011). Most of these studies show that the effect of reducing costs on business formalization is relatively modest, with only a few demonstrating a significant increase in the number of businesses that formalize as a result. For example, Rocha *et al.* (2018) found that cutting taxes and reducing the costs of formalization procedures were an incentive for Brazilian informal firms to formalize. However, the limited impact of cost-reduction interventions raises questions about the conclusions of the exclusion model. Some other studies have also looked at the impact of increasing the benefits of business registration. Indeed, in an attempt to understand the rational exit model, Jaramillo (2013) and Fandl and Bustamante (2016) studied the effect of monetary incentives on formalizing. However, they reported no significant change in business registration. Additionally, no effect on formalization was found concerning the microcredit offered by the Brazilian public bank (Goldszmidt *et al.*, 2018). Differently, De Mel *et al.* (2013) found a large positive impact after offering monetary incentives for registration in Sri Lanka.

Another set of studies looked into the parasite model. For instance, De Giorgi *et al.* (2017) did not find a greater level of formalization when firms were visited more by tax officers in Bangladesh. Differently, Galiani *et al.* (2017) used an experimental design to evaluate the impact of meetings with chamber of commerce officers on the benefits of business licensing. However, they found that the positive effect of these meetings was short-lived, as many firms

failed to renew their license after one year. Under the same perspective, some other studies have focused on the impact of information sessions and assistance meetings on formalization. De Giorgi and Rahman (2013) found that firms are more likely to register if they receive information about procedures and benefits. A similar result was found by Kaiser and Menkhoff (2018), who combined the benefits of the training on the formalization procedures with information about the costs and risks of operating informally. Finally, Cabrera *et al.* (2016) discovered that one-on-one assistance meetings have a greater impact on compliance with labor regulations when combined with monetary incentives.

Overall, the findings of micro-level studies on formalization interventions are inconsistent and varied. Some studies show conflicting results even for the same kind of reform in different countries or in the same country with different cutoff dates (Fajnzylber *et al.*, 2011 vs. Monteiro & Assunção, 2012). Additionally, different interventions can have varying effects depending on the indicator of formality being considered, such as registration, license, tax code, or bookkeeping of balance sheet. For example, a reform aimed at simplifying the process of registering a business in Mexico led to a positive impact on firm registration but did not affect other measures of formality (Aparicio, 2014). Similar results were found for Perú by Díaz *et al.* (2018).

2.2. Formal Vs. Informal Businesses: R&D, Innovation and Productivity

The growing importance of innovation in developing countries has sparked a new area of research. A recent branch of the literature specifically focuses on the introduction of new products and services by agents not included in the formal economy. In this respect, the resourcefulness, ingenuity, and adaptability of individuals living in poverty are recognized to be the main sources of local innovation. Thus, when evaluating the impact of innovation on a firm's performance in many developing nations, it is crucial to acknowledge the presence of a dual-economy system consisting of formal and informal businesses.

As a matter of fact, the literature on the role of innovation on firms' growth in low-income countries has grown in recent years. Many studies have focused on the impact of product or process innovations on different firms' performances and several empirical studies found a positive correlation between innovation and firms' productivity. For example, Mahemba and Bruijn (2003) surveyed small-medium-enterprises (SMEs) in Tanzania and found a positive association between innovativeness and various measures of firms' growth. Similarly, Gebreeyesus (2009) found strong evidence in Ethiopian SMEs that innovators grew faster in terms of employment than non-innovators. In Sri Lanka, De Mel *et al.* (2009) found a positive relationship between innovation and the profits of SMEs. Thus, this evidence suggests that innovation has a positive impact on firms' profits and employment growth. Nevertheless, a growing body of research has also shown a weaker relationship between innovations and firms' performances in emerging economies. For example, Goedhuys *et al.* (2008, 2014) discovered that the firm's productivity in Tanzania was not improved by R&D, product innovation, or process innovation, but rather by the business environment. These findings suggest that the link between R&D, innovation, and productivity is weaker in developing countries compared to developed ones. According to the widely accepted belief, while the impact of innovation on firm growth in developed countries has been widely documented, its effect in developing countries is only partially understood. In addition, as noted by Wunsch-Vincent and Kraemer-Mbula (2016), the lack of data and difficulties in measuring innovation have limited the empirical research on the connection between innovation and firm growth in low-income countries, especially with respect to informal firms.

In the context of developing countries, measuring the impact of the firms' informal status and/or firms' innovations on their productivity is challenging also because of the marginal role that R&D investments play for the majority of micro and small (informal) firms. However, as La Porta and Shleifer (2014) noticed, since economic

growth can help to reduce informality, investigating the innovative practices of informal firms and their impact on growth could be a critical factor in this process of formalization. In their survey on informality and development, the authors presented five key characteristics of informal firms in developing countries. The informal firms (a) account for a significant number of enterprises at the aggregate level and (b) tend to avoid some tax payments and government regulations. On the other hand, the informal sector often includes (c) small and (d) inefficient firms, also because (e) informal entrepreneurs have a limited education. Thus, it leads to low productivity levels and weaker economic growth.

The likelihood of firms in the formal and informal sectors to invest in R&D and to adopt and diffuse innovations is therefore shaped by their characteristics and capabilities, as demonstrated by Wunsch-Vincent and Kraemer-Mbula (2016). Formal establishments, with their greater human and financial resources, are more likely to engage in collaborative innovation activities with other firms and foreign organizations and institutions (Oyelaran-Oyeyinka *et al.*, 1996). On the other hand, informal firms typically lack financial resources and may rely more on entrepreneurs' drive and the constraints of their operating environment (Robson *et al.*, 2009). Although entrepreneurs' ingenuity has been viewed as the driving force behind innovation for informal firms (Prahalad, 2012), the literature has mostly focused on observable indicators, such as the firm's size, and workers' and entrepreneurs' education, as factors that determine innovation. An exception is found in De Mel *et al.* (2009), who use a variety of indicators to support the argument that the success of informal enterprises in Sri Lanka is shaped not only by skills but also by risk aversion and the business savvy of their owners.

Small firm size is one of the defining features of informal establishments. This aspect, characterizing the extent of a company's operations, has been deemed a hindrance to innovation in several

studies (De Mel *et al.*, 2009; Gebreeyesus, 2009; Robson *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, the absence of adequate resources in the education system in many low-income countries prompts non-formal training to become the primary means of acquiring knowledge, along with on-the-job learning (Oyelaran-Oyeyinka & Lal, 2006). Nevertheless, as indicated by Yuki (2007), the majority of works in the informal sector are low-skilled, causing employers to view employee training as unnecessary and unhelpful. Moreover, informal firms, free from formal employment contracts, have the freedom to dismiss employees with little to no compensation (Harris, 2014a). Thus, the lack of stability in the workforce, along with the possibility of trained employees benefiting competitors, could reduce the incentive for informal firms to invest in employee formal training (Harris, 2014b). However, since informal firms are not bound by labor regulations, their employment strategies are usually flexible, allowing them to easily adjust their workforce in case of necessity (Ingram *et al.*, 2007). In turn, flexible employment adjustments might mitigate the negative effects of product market uncertainty on firms' innovative efforts (Di Cintio & Grassi, 2017).

Nonetheless, informal firms are vulnerable to having their innovative products or services stolen by competitors due to the lack of protection offered by intellectual property rights (Harris, 2014b). Moreover, Schipper (2014) suggests that even if informal firms are able to introduce new and innovative products or services, they might face challenges in terms of accessing distribution channels. The limited access to marketing channels and media restricts the ability of these firms to reap the benefits of their innovations (Teece, 1986). Anyway, informal firms often concentrate on survival and make investments that bring quick returns (Harris, 2014c). As a result, they are less likely to allocate financial resources toward R&D. According to Bu and Cuervo-Cazurra (2020), informal firms that began as such may prioritize short-term goals over innovation, resulting in lower levels of innovation compared to formally established

firms. Similarly, Mendi and Mudida (2017) found that past informality status hurts technological innovations in Kenya. Therefore, long-term investments - such as engaging in R&D activities (Kuo *et al.*, 2018) - may be less common among informal firms. Indeed, according to Assefa *et al.* (2022), the negative relationship between informality and innovation is due to low investments in R&D.

However, research has also shown that small firms in the informal sector are able to innovate and acquire new knowledge. Von Hippel (2005) explains that informal firms are encouraged to innovate even when the economic returns of the product they are creating are low because, anyway, they benefit from the process of developing or modifying an existing product. Moreover, Fu *et al.* (2018) offer empirical insights into the impact of innovation on the productivity of formal and informal firms in Ghana. Their study revealed that formal firms tend to experience a stronger effect on productivity from technological innovations, but both formal and informal firms benefit equally from non-technological innovations.

Whereas the role of innovation on firms' productivity in developed countries is largely documented, its impact in developing countries is still only partially understood, mainly across informal firms. Difficulties related to data availability on informal firms and the measurement of their innovation input and output have limited the empirical studies in emerging economies. Moreover, the literature has focused either on the effects of policy interventions aimed at promoting the formalization of informal firms or on the effects that different levels of firms' productivity may have on the *switching to the formal status* of existing informal firms. Therefore, to the best of our knowledge, there are no studies that, instead, analyze the effects of the *transition from an informal to a formal status* on firms' innovativeness and productivity.

This paper aims to fill this gap by analyzing data from the Enterprise Survey in Vietnam. In particular, as will be explained in detail in the following sections, we will try to answer three main research

questions that inspired our work: 1) “*In the context of emerging countries with both formal and informal firms, how does R&D and innovation affect firms’ productivity?*”; 2) “*Are there differences between formal and informal firms?*”; 3) “*Could the transition from informal to formal status enhance firms’ innovativeness and productivity?*”.

3. EMPIRICAL MODEL

Our empirical strategy applies a structural model (Crépon *et al.*, 1998) to answer our research questions. Specifically, the empirical model is constructed in three stages and includes three equations to account for the endogeneity of firms’ innovation efforts and outcomes. In the first stage, we consider the issue of under-reporting of R&D expenditures and estimate an *R&D input function* at time. Then, in the second stage, we estimate a *knowledge production function* at time that reflects the firms’ probability of introducing innovations in the next two years. Finally, in the last stage, we estimate a *productivity function* at time to evaluate how innovation affects firms’ labor productivity in the following two years. Hence, our empirical methodology takes into account a two-year lagged time between each step to alleviate potential problems of endogeneity and reverse causality. In this way, we can also be more confident that R&D investments have enough time to fully deploy their effects on innovation outcomes and that innovations, in turn, have a useful time span to improve labor productivity.

Since a firm’s productivity represents the ability of a firm to generate greater outputs with fewer inputs, we suppose firms have a (CRS) Cobb-Douglas production function $Y_i = A_i * K_i^{\alpha_k} * L_i^{\alpha_L}$, where firm-level output, Y_i is a function of inputs of capital (K_i), labor (L_i) and knowledge (A_i). Thus, the term A_i is the portion of output that cannot be directly explained from physical inputs. It represents a proxy of the total know-how and knowledge incorporated into the firm’s production process. Hence, by using this model we can easily estimate the effects of innovations (i.e. knowledge) on the firm’s productivity, by taking into account that

higher R&D investments may help firms to introduce innovations. To answer our research questions, these relationships are evaluated by considering the effects of informality on the different firms' performances in the specific way described in what follows.

As suggested by Kleinknecht (1987) and confirmed by Santarelli and Sterlacchini (1990), self-reported R&D measures for small and medium enterprises may severely underestimate their innovation investments. The presence of informal innovation activities, the peculiar type of R&D being undertaken, or the absence of structured R&D departments are all likely to be factors influencing the declared R&D effort (Roper, 1999) and are very likely to be also more relevant when focusing on informal firms in developing countries. Thus, self-reported R&D expenditure often fails to adequately describe the actual innovative investments of this kind of firms. The estimates of the R&D intensity equation are thus a necessary step to obtain a better and actual proxy of the innovative investments carried out by firms in our sample.¹ Therefore, especially to account for the under-reporting of R&D of informal firms, we assume that a latent variable $\overline{R\&D}$ is related to a set of independent control variables, x_{1i} , and to the firm's informality status, INF_i , according to the following standard *type I Tobit model*:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{R\&D}_i &= \gamma_1 * INF_i + \beta_1 * x_{1i} + \alpha + v_i \\ R\&D_i &= \begin{cases} \overline{R\&D}_i, & \overline{R\&D}_i > c \\ 0, & \overline{R\&D}_i \leq c \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where γ_1 and β_1 are coefficients to be estimated, α is a constant term, v_i is the error component, and c is the threshold beyond which R&D is observed.² The choice of the *Tobit model* is common in innovation studies where some variables are only observed for the innovating firms. Therefore, we interpret the firm's R&D efforts ($R\&D_i$) as a corner solution response variable, which takes the

¹ A similar approach can be found in Crépon et al. (1998) and Hall et al. (2009).

² A detailed description of the independent variables used in the regression is provided in section 4.

value 0 with positive probability while it is a continuous variable over strictly positive values. This means that some firms may not find it optimal to engage in R&D activities.¹ From this *R&D input function*, we take the predicted values as a firm-level proxy of actual R&D intensity ($\widehat{R\&D}$).²

In the second stage, we delve into the relationship between R&D intensity (i.e. innovation input) and innovation output. Specifically, we will refer to the introduction of both *radical* (i.e. firms introduced new products) and *soft innovations* (i.e. firms made any improvements to existing products). In particular, in considering the *knowledge production function* that reflects the firms' probability of introducing innovations, we run a *Probit model* in which we regress the unobservable latent variable ($\widehat{Inn}$) on the "transition to formality status" ($Trans_FORM_i$) in the time span between time t and time $t + 2$, the estimated R&D intensity ($\widehat{R\&D}$) and a set of independent control covariates (x_{2i}):

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{Inn}_i &= \gamma_2 * Trans_FORM_i + \theta * \widehat{R\&D}_i + \beta_2 * x_{2i} + \delta + \varepsilon_i \\ Inn_i &= \begin{cases} 1, & \widehat{Inn}_i > 0 \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where γ_2 , θ , and β_2 are coefficients to be estimated, δ is a constant term, and ε is the error component. Thus, for each firm, Inn_i is the observed binary variable equal to 1 if a firm introduced innovations. We use these estimates to obtain predicted values of the firms' probability to introduce innovations ($\widehat{Inn}_i$), which are then included in the third stage of our structural model as the key determinants of firms' labor productivity.³

¹ It is worth noting that in this step, we also control for the self-selection of firms into R&D through a Two-stage Least Square (2SLS) model and, similar to Hall *et al.* (2009), we reject the hypothesis of self-selection. Consequently, we estimate the R&D equation by a *Tobit* regression without the inclusion of a correction term for selectivity.

² Note that, implicitly, predicted values of R&D reflect both official and informal R&D investments made by firms.

³ Using these predicted probabilities instead of the observed indicators is a way to address the issue of potential endogeneity of the knowledge inputs.

The last stage of our empirical model is devoted to studying the impact of both firms' "transition to formality status" ($Trans_FORM_i$) and innovation ($\widehat{Inn}_i$) on their labor productivity (y_i). Therefore, in order to capture the differences in productivity between formal and informal innovative firms, we include an interaction term between these two main regressors. It is worth noticing that while the firm's productivity is evaluated at time $t + 4$, the probability of innovation refers to time $t + 2$ and the dummy related to the transition into a *formal status* indicates if the same firm switched from informal to formal status in the time span between time t and time $t + 4$. Thus, we estimate the firms' *productivity function* through the following OLS equation:

$$y_i = \gamma_3 * (Trans_FORM_i * \widehat{Inn}_i) + \vartheta * \widehat{Inn}_i + \beta_3 * x_{3i} + \varphi + \mu_i \quad (3)$$

where γ_3 , ϑ , β_3 and φ are coefficients to be estimated, φ is a constant term and μ is the error term.¹

It is worth noting that we rely on an exclusion restriction to identify the parameters of the *knowledge production function* from those of the *productivity function*, i.e. at least one significant explanatory variable in the knowledge equation does not appear in the productivity equation. This variable should directly affect innovation and affect productivity only indirectly through innovation. Given the absence of adequate resources in the education system in many low-income countries, government assistance in *human resource training* could be a good candidate to instrument the firms' probability to innovate.² Thus, as an exclusion-restriction, we refer to a dummy variable that

¹ The second and third stages also include the squared terms of the main regressors to account for any non-linear effects.

² In the original CDM model, innovation is instrumented in the productivity equation directly with the R&D expenditures. Thus, Crépon *et al.* (1998) used just two stages instead of three stages as in our model. However, in our opinion, and as already mentioned, the estimation of the unofficial R&D intensity is a necessary step to obtain a better proxy of the innovative investments carried out by informal firms in developing countries.

reflects whether or not firms “Received government assistance in 2012 for Human Resource Training Programmes”, being confident that the impact of government assistance would enhance firms’ innovations and affect productivity through innovations.

At the same time, since an increase in firms’ productivity could stimulate the transition of firms from an informal to a formal status, we also need to consider that the variables y_i and $Trans_FORM_i$ could be both endogenous. Indeed, since more productive firms may have better opportunities to operate inside the formal and regulatory framework, a higher level of productivity could have a reverse causality effect that may result in a driven factor of their “transition to formality status”. Therefore, as a *robustness check*, we perform our analysis under a different estimation methodology. In particular, we estimate a simultaneous-equations system by using a *full-maximum-likelihood* (instead of multi-separated steps) estimator, where both firms’ productivity and the “transition to formality status” are supposed to be endogenous.¹ Hence, in the *productivity function* at time $t + 4$, $Trans_FORM_i$ is instrumented with the ratio between the amount of “total fees-and-taxes” paid by firms and firms’ employment at time.

We are aware that the identification of causal effects would require the availability of panel data and that, in the absence of such data, we will only be able to provide suggestive evidence of dependencies among variables. Nevertheless, given the lack of previous work on these relationships, we believe our empirical results provide preliminary insight that could be very useful in shaping future research on this topic.

4. DATA AND VARIABLES DESCRIPTION

Our study is based on the data from the 2011, 2013, and 2015 results of the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprise (MSME) Sur-

¹ Simultaneous estimations accounting for a full-covariance structure are, in general, also more efficient.

vey in Vietnam. The surveys are conducted by the United Nations University World Institute for Development Economics Research (UNU-WIDER) in collaboration with the University of Copenhagen, and two Vietnamese partners: the Central Institute for Economic Management (CIEM, Vietnam) and the Institute for Labor Studies and Social Affairs (ILSSA, Vietnam). Each survey provides detailed information on more than 2,500 formal and informal MSMEs in the Vietnamese private manufacturing sector.

In particular, the surveys consist of three modules: (1) a main enterprise questionnaire; (2) an employee questionnaire; and (3) an economic accounts questionnaire. In this study, we focus especially on (1) the enterprise questionnaire that provides detailed information on firm performance, enterprise history, employment, business environment, and owner background characteristics, and (2) the economic accounts questionnaire which contains information on firms' revenues, investments, assets, liabilities and taxes.

The original sample includes 2,512 firms in the wave of 2011; 2,542 firms in the wave of 2013, and 2,650 firms in the last wave of 2015. Each wave reports information related to the previous two years and although the sample was adjusted slightly over time, the questionnaires remained nearly the same. Specifically, the sample included a wide range of firms operating in ten Vietnamese provinces: private, collectives, partnerships, private limited enterprises, and joint stock enterprises. The surveys were administered in the northern, central, and southern regions of the country: *Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Ha Tay, Hai Phong, Long An, Phu Tho, Quang Nam, Nghe An, Khanh Hoa, and Lam Dong*. Stratified sampling ensures representation by ownership type across the ten provinces by including non-state locally-owned manufacturing enterprises only and excluding joint stock companies with state capital and joint ventures with foreign capital. Nevertheless, the inclusion of both formal and informal domestic private firms makes this survey unique compared with other firm-level datasets for Vietnam, such as the GSO's annual Enterprises Survey or the World

Bank's Enterprise Survey, which only cover formal firms (i.e. firms that are registered and have a tax code).

To implement our empirical model, we rely on three key dependent variables, i.e., the *firms' labor productivity*, the *radical or soft innovations* introduced by firms, and their *R&D intensity*. In particular, we compute R&D intensity (measured in the fiscal year 2010) as the ratio between R&D expenditure and turnover, while innovation (measured in the fiscal year 2012) is defined as a dummy equal to one if a firm introduced new products or made any improvements to existing products. Finally, as a measure of labor productivity (measured in the fiscal year 2014), we refer to the *sales-per-employee* at the firm level, which is widely used in innovation literature to capture firms' productivity.

We control for several aspects common in similar studies. A specific impact on the R&D intensity may be related to the firm's *manager/owner education* and the implementation of *training activities for employees*. Moreover, since larger firms are expected to better exploit economies of scope and scale, we also control for the firm size, measured by the *level of employment*. Other controls common to all the estimation stages include: a dummy to distinguish between (family business) *households and non-household firms*; a dummy variable indicating if firms incurred *bribes* or other informal payments; *firm liquidity* measured as the ratio between the amount of cash-and-deposit and turnover; *firm age*; *sectors* and *provinces* dummies. Moreover, in the 2015 survey, we were also able to find information on the firm's *manager risk propensity*. Hence, we consider this variable (eleven graduations from 0 to 10; risk aversion = 0 - risk loving = 10) as an additional regressor in the estimation of the productivity function. Moreover, since firms engaging in internationalization activities constitute a small minority, we were unable to find a significant number of firms who declared their share of export over turnover. Nonetheless, we use a dummy variable to control whether a firm has an *internationally recognized quality certificate*. Obviously, in the estimation of the

firm's productivity, we finally include the capital input measured through the value of the *firm's total assets-per-employee*.

We merge the data from the three mentioned waves and exclude observations with inconsistent or missing information on the relevant variables. Due to the lack of these pieces of information, the sample in our estimation was limited to 1,050 firms, for which we can track the dynamics from a firm's R&D investment in 2010, to innovations introduced in 2012, to productivity in 2014. *Table 1* summarizes the descriptive statistics.

As in other developing countries, on average, R&D intensity is particularly low and with high variability, mainly because many enterprises do not report official R&D investments. In our sample, about 17% of firms introduced new products or improved the existing ones. However, a large proportion of these innovations are *soft* innovations (16.95%) rather than *radical* innovations (0.67%). Labor productivity (sales-per-employee) is also not particularly high, and a very high standard error can be observed (from a minimum of about 4 billion to a maximum of 4.303 billion VDN). Moreover, in 2010, nearly 46% of enterprises were informal. However, while 8.95% of informal enterprises transited into the formal economy in 2012, the transition rate is shown to be much higher after 4 years (37.71%). This implies that the government policies devoted to this goal have been quite successful. Managers with a college or university education are just under 11%, and only 3.71% of enterprises provide job training to their employees. On average, there are about 9 employees per enterprise, with a maximum of 367 and a minimum of only one entrepreneur with no employees. Consistently, around 92% of enterprises in the sample belong to family business households. Even though not reported in the table to save space, a significant proportion of households dominate the following three industries: Food Processing (34.29%), Wood Processing (11.11%), and Fabricated Metal Products (17.91%). 67.52%

of firms incurred bribes or other informal payments and the level of liquidity in terms of cash and deposits is particularly modest. While, as expected, the low engagement in international activity is clearly shown by a low level of international quality certification (2.48%), surprisingly Vietnamese entrepreneurs show, that on average, they do not particularly care about risk (the mean of risk aversion is 3.7 on a scale from 0 to 10).

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
R&D Intensity 2010	0.0023	0.0443	0	1.1635
Innovation 2012	0.1724	0.3779	0	1
Radical Innovation 2012	0.0067	0.0814	0	1
Soft Innovation 2012	0.1695	0.3754	0	1
Sales-per-employee 2014 (billions VDN)	251.1283	307.5848	3.9545	4,303.5060
Informal 2010	0.4676	0.4992	0	1
Transition to Formal 2012	0.0895	0.2856	0	1
Transition to Formal 2010-2014	0.3771	0.4849	0	1
Manager education	0.1086	0.3112	0	1
On-the-Job Training	0.0371	0.1892	0	1
Employment	9.1638	20.4337	1	367
Household	0.9190	0.2729	0	1
Bribes	0.6752	0.4685	0	1
Liquidity	0.0001	0.0003	0	0.004
Age	19.1029	9.6022	2	61
Risk Propensity	3.725	2.448	0	10
International Certification	0.0248	0.1555	0	1
Asset-per-employee (billions VDN)	0.3666	0.5430	0.0391	6.0500
Observations	1,050			

5. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

As discussed earlier, to analyze the relationship among R&D, innovation, and productivity at the firm level, we relied on a modi-

fied version of the model proposed by Crépon *et al.* (1998). In order to account for a firm's innovations not necessarily based on formal R&D activities – those which are likely to be also most important for the informal MSMEs – we do not restrict estimations just to official R&D performing firms. Thus, our first step consists of the estimation of an *R&D input function* at time t (in our model in the fiscal year 2010), that is the process that leads formal and informal firms to decide whether to undertake R&D investments or not and how much to invest on R&D. Differently, the second step involves a *knowledge production function* at time $t+2$ (in our model in the fiscal year 2012), in which the predicted R&D intensity (that considers both official and informal investments in R&D) is one of the inputs and *radical* or *soft* innovations are the outputs. Finally, the third step concerns a simple *productivity function* at time $t+4$ (in our model in the fiscal year 2014) in which knowledge (i.e., the predicted probability to introduce *radical* or *soft* innovations) is among the main inputs. Moreover, to evaluate the effect of the *transition in the formal status* on firms' performances, in the last two steps we consider an additional regressor which indicates whether or not a firm switched *from an informal to a formal status*.

Table 2 reports the estimation of the *R&D input function*. The first column reports the determinants of R&D, while the last two columns report estimated coefficients and standard errors. As expected, the results clearly show that informal firms invest less in R&D than formal firms. Differently, the higher education of managers and on-the-job training positively affect the firm's R&D intensity. Since greater financial resources can push R&D investments, firms' liquidity also increases firms' R&D. Moreover, younger firms are more likely to produce a more intense effort in innovative activities. Inversely, household firms and those who incurred bribes show a lower R&D intensity. Finally, the size of the firm – measured as the level of employment – does not seem to explicate a significant effect on R&D.

Table 2: R&D Input Function

	Coefficient	Std. Err.
Informal	-0.574***	(0.088)
Manager education	0.349***	(0.103)
On-the-Job Training	0.427***	(0.082)
Household	-0.851***	(0.098)
Bribes	-0.274***	(0.095)
Liquidity	248.451***	(75.396)
Age	-0.036***	(0.006)
Employment	0.025	(0.038)
Constant	-4.156***	(0.106)
Pseudo R2	0.2826	
Sigma	0.815***	(0.043)
Industry dummies	Yes	
Province dummies	Yes	
Observations	1,050	

Notes: The dependent variable is the (log) R&D intensity. The R&D Input Function is estimated through a Tobit model. All continuous variables are in logs. Standard errors in parentheses. ***, **, * denote, respectively, significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10%. Estimates are carried out on a sample of 1,050 observations observed in the fiscal year 2010.

Table 3: Knowledge Production Function

	Coefficient	Std. Err.
Instrument	0.587*	(0.339)
R&D Intensity 2010	35.880*	(20.723)
R&D Intensity 2010 (squared)	-1025.690*	(565.978)
Transition to Formal 2010-2012	0.570***	(0.148)
Household	-0.013	(0.170)
Bribes	-0.041	(0.100)
Liquidity	94.107	(108.598)
Age	0.004	(0.005)
Employment	0.387***	(0.075)
Constant	-1.941***	(0.282)
Pseudo R2	0.079	
Industry dummies	Yes	
Province dummies	Yes	
Observations	1,050	

Notes: The dependent variable is a dummy equal to one if a firm introduced Radical or Soft innovations. The Knowledge Production Function is estimated through a Probit model. As an instrument, we use the Received government assistance in 2012 for Human Resource Training Programmes. R&D intensity is given by the predicted values of the first stage. All continuous variables are in logs. Standard errors in parentheses. ***, **, * denote, respectively, significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10%. Estimates are carried out on a sample of 1,050 observations observed in the fiscal year 2012.

We now turn to the estimation of the R&D-innovations relationship. The estimated coefficients of the *knowledge production function* are reported in *Table 3*. First of all, our instrument – the *Received government assistance in 2012 for Human Resource Training Programmes* – is a significant predictor of the firms' probability to introduce *Radical* and *Soft* innovation. As expected, the R&D intensity clearly has a positive and significant impact on the firms' likelihood to innovate, even though the negative sign of the squared term indicates a decreasing positive effect. This result is not a surprise since most of the mainstream literature has already highlighted the importance of R&D investments on innovation. We also find that the dummies relative to household firms and bribe payments are not among the significant determinants of innovations, as well as their liquidity and age. Differently, larger firms show a higher probability of innovating. More important for our study is the significant and positive coefficient of the regressor linked to the firm's *transition to a formal status*. Those informal firms who switched to the formal economy show better performances in terms of innovation. At the same time, this result implicitly means that those firms who remain informal are less likely to introduce innovation in the two years following their R&D investments.

Table 4 reports the results of the third stage of our structural model. Consistent with most of the literature on the role of innovation, our empirical model shows a positive impact of innovations on firms' productivity. Indeed, we support the widespread idea that more innovative firms experience higher labor productivity.

Table 4: Productivity Function

	Coefficient	Std. Err.
Innovation Probability (Radical and Soft)	2.793***	(0.712)

Innovation Probability (squared)	-3.520***	(1.235)
Transition to Formal 2010-2014 * Innovation	-1.515***	(0.564)
Transition to Formal 2010-2014 * Innovation (squared)	1.784	(1.490)
Employment	-0.057	(0.050)
Asset-per-employee	0.297***	(0.023)
International Certification	1.078***	(0.208)
Risk Propensity	0.257***	(0.090)
Bribes	0.229***	(0.053)
Liquidity	-670.151***	(108.250)
Age	-0.007***	(0.002)
Constant	10.251***	(0.193)
R2	0.336	
Industry dummies	Yes	
Province dummies	Yes	
Observations	1,050	

Notes: The dependent variable is the (log) sales-per-employee. The Productivity Function is estimated through an OLS model. Innovation Probability is given by the predicted values of the second stage. All continuous variables are in logs. Standard errors in parentheses. ***, **, * denote, respectively, significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10%. Estimates are carried out on a sample of 1,050 observations observed in the fiscal year 2014.

However, while we found that formal firms are more likely to introduce innovation, our results also reveal that – against all odds – the ‘*underdog*’ informal firms show a higher level of productivity when they are able to innovate. Indeed, the negative and highly significant coefficient of the interaction term between the *transition to formal status* and the innovation probability indicates that those firms that remain informal and are able to introduce *radical* or *soft* innovations exhibit greater labor productivity. In particular, the marginal effect of innovations on productivity turns out to be 1.24, which is the ratio of the percentage change in our dependent variable to the percentage change in the innovation probability (i.e. an elasticity measure). Thus, it means that, for instance, a 10% increase in the innovation probability induces a 12.4% increase in the firm’s labor productivity. Nevertheless, by computing the marginal effect of the *transition to a formal*

status on productivity, we find a value of -0.187 . Thus, an innovative informal firm shrinks its productivity by 0.187 percentage points by switching from an informal to a formal status.

To explore these results more in-depth, we investigate how our estimations change if we distinguish between *radical* and *soft* innovation. Specifically, we re-estimate both the second and third stages of the empirical model by disentangling how R&D investments affect the probability of introducing new products separately from those of improving the existing ones. *Table 5* shows the results of the second stage, where the coefficients of the main regressors continue to hold the same signs as before, although their magnitudes are slightly different from those shown in *Table 3*. However, they remain still appropriately significant.

Table 5: Knowledge Production Function - Radical and Soft Innovations

	Radical Innovations		Soft Innovations	
	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Coefficient	Std. Err.
Instrument	0.971**	(0.453)	0.372*	(0.353)
R&D Intensity 2010	89.987***	(27.895)	35.474*	(20.786)
R&D Intensity 2010 (squared)	-1228.558**	(516.237)	-1013.304*	(563.039)
Transition to Formal 2012	0.825***	(0.303)	0.544***	(0.148)
Household	-0.302	(0.264)	0.022	(0.172)
Bribes	-0.03	(0.284)	-0.055	(0.101)
Liquidity	68.188	(103.063)	87.43	(110.147)
Age	0.011*	(0.007)	0.003	(0.005)
Employment	-0.095	(0.232)	0.407***	(0.075)
Constant	-2.828***	(0.610)	-1.997***	(0.285)
Pseudo R2	0.163		0.077	
Industry dummies	Yes		Yes	
Province dummies	Yes		Yes	
Observations	1,050		1,050	

Notes: The dependent variable is a dummy equal to one if a firm introduced Radical or Soft innovations. The Knowledge Production Function is estimated through a Probit model. As an instrument, we use the Received government assistance in 2012 for Human Resource Training Programmes.

R&D intensity is given by the predicted values of the first stage. All continuous variables are in logs. Standard errors in parentheses. ***, **, * denote, respectively, significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10%. Estimates are carried out on a sample of 1,050 observations observed in the fiscal year 2012.

As for the third stage, *Table 6* reports the estimation results on the productivity function, by distinguishing between the probability of introducing *radical* or *soft* innovations. The signs of the coefficients are the same as those previously shown in *Table 4*. It is evident, however, that the magnitude of the effects of *radical* innovations is greater than that of *soft* innovations. Specifically, while the marginal effect of radical innovations on productivity amounts to 7.46, that of the soft innovations sums to 1.30. On the other hand, the marginal effect of the *transition to a formal status* is higher with respect to panel-b (−0.173) than that referred to panel-a (−0.058). Therefore, while a *soft*-innovative informal firm shrinks its productivity by 0.173 percentage points by switching from an informal to a formal status, this switch reduces the productivity of a *radical*-innovative informal firm by 0.058 percentage points. Even small in magnitude, these results suggest that, while encouraging policy actions may transform some informal firms into formal ones, such policies could not be sufficient to increase their productivity.

Table 6: Productivity Function - Radical and Soft Innovations

	(a) Radical Innovations		(b) Soft Innovations	
	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Coefficient	Std. Err.
Innovation Probability	13.106***	(4.235)	2.934***	(0.733)
Innovation Probability (squared)	-94.865**	(48.302)	-3.808***	(1.289)
Transition to Formal 2010-2014 * Innovation	-13.244***	(4.943)	-1.287**	(0.606)
Transition to Formal 2010-2014 * Innovation (squared)	108.558**	(49.277)	1.124	(1.677)
Employment	0.006	(0.041)	-0.051	(0.050)
Asset-per-employee	0.308***	(0.023)	0.297***	(0.023)
International Certification	1.043***	(0.180)	1.077***	(0.206)
Risk Propensity	0.278***	(0.090)	0.257***	(0.090)
Bribes	0.241***	(0.053)	0.228***	(0.053)

Liquidity	-678.087***	(115.858)	-670.399***	(107.811)
Age	-0.007***	(0.002)	-0.007***	(0.002)
Constant	10.296***	(0.184)	10.222***	(0.195)
R2	0.327		0.336	
Industry dummies	Yes		Yes	
Province dummies	Yes		Yes	
Observations	1,050		1,050	

Notes: The dependent variable is the (log) sales-per-employee. The Productivity Function is estimated through an OLS model. Innovation Probability is given by the predicted values of the second stage: Panel (a) considers Radical innovations, Panel (b) Soft innovations. All continuous variables are in logs. Standard errors in parentheses. ***, **, * denote, respectively, significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10%. Estimates are carried out on a sample of 1,050 observations observed in the fiscal year 2014.

Table 7: Productivity Function - Simultaneous-Equations System (full-maximum-likelihood estimator)

	Panel (a)		Panel (b)		Panel (c)	
Second stage: Productivity function						
	Coefficient	Std.Err.	Coefficient	Std.Err.	Coefficient	Std.Err.
Innovation Probability	2.872***	(0.702)	10.437*	(5.353)	2.970***	(0.709)
Innovation Probability (squared)	-3.637***	(1.152)	-72.108	(51.438)	-3.862***	(1.172)
Transition to Formal 2010-2014 * Innovation	-1.788**	(0.846)	-6.911	(6.854)	-1.427	(0.898)
Transition to Formal 2010-2014 * Innovation (squared)	2.155	(1.558)	66.757	(58.318)	1.324	(1.727)
Employment	-0.059	(0.043)	0.006	(0.034)	-0.052	(0.044)
Asset-per-employee	0.297***	(0.022)	0.304***	(0.022)	0.297***	(0.022)
International Certification	1.075***	(0.311)	1.056***	(0.313)	1.075***	(0.311)
Risk Propensity	0.256***	(0.088)	0.278***	(0.088)	0.257***	(0.088)
Bribes	0.228***	(0.052)	0.244***	(0.052)	0.228***	(0.052)
Liquidity	-670.152***	(66.786)	-675.806***	(67.296)	-670.399***	(66.763)
Age	-0.007***	(0.002)	-0.007***	(0.002)	-0.007***	(0.002)
Constant	10.258***	(0.180)	10.317***	(0.174)	10.226***	(0.180)
First stage: Transition to formal 2010-2014						
Total fees and taxes per employee	-0.382***	(0.034)	-0.379***	(0.034)	-0.382***	(0.034)

Sigma	-0.399***	(0.022)	-0.392***	(0.022)	-0.400***	(0.022)
Rho	0.043	(0.104)	-0.118*	(0.072)	0.021	(0.106)
Industry dummies	Yes		Yes		Yes	
Province dummies	Yes		Yes		Yes	
Observations	1,050		1,050		1,050	

Notes: The dependent variable in the first stage is a dummy equal to one if a firm switches from the informal to the formal status in the time span between 2010-2014. The transition into a formal status is instrumented with the “total fees-and-taxes-per-employee” paid by firms at time t . Further details on the other regressors included in the first stage are available upon request. The dependent variable in the second stage is the (log) sales-per-employee. Innovation Probability is given by the predicted values of the Knowledge Production Function: Panel (a) considers both Radical and Soft innovation, Panel (b) just Radical innovations, Panel (c) just Soft innovations. All continuous variables are in logs. Standard errors in parentheses. ***, **, * denote, respectively, significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10%. Estimates are carried out on a sample of 1,050 observations observed in the fiscal year 2014.

We have also re-estimated the empirical model to be compelling for even the most skeptical readers about the validity of the previous results. As already mentioned in section 3, we perform a *robustness check* of our analysis using a different estimation methodology. In particular, we refer to a *full-maximum-likelihood* estimator of a simultaneous-equations system, where both firms’ productivity and the “*transition to formality status*” are supposed to be endogenous. Specifically, to estimate the *productivity function* at time $t+4$, we instrumented the “*transition to formality status*” with the “*total fees-and-taxes-per-employee*” paid by firms at time t .

Table 7 clearly shows the stability of our results, also by considering that a higher level of productivity could have a reverse causality effect which may result in a driven factor of firms’ “*transition to formality status*”. Thus, similarly to previous results, while innovations positively impact firms’ productivity, the transition to a formal status exerts a negative effect on the productivity of innovative informal firms.

Hence, since our study found successful innovative informal firms more productive than formal ones, economic policies should encourage their transition to the formal sector, but they should also leave them a high level of flexibility. In this way, such policies could

enhance firms' innovation, increase their productivity, and drive economic progress in Vietnam. In this context, our paper suggests policies fostering an economic environment where informal firms grow as successful innovators.

Summing up, we found three significant results. First, informal firms – on average – invest less in R&D than formal firms. However, the higher education of managers and employee on-the-job training can push R&D investments, as well as greater financial resources. Second, those informal firms who do not switch to the formal sector are less likely to introduce innovation in the two years following their R&D investments. Third, since the transition to a formal status exerts a negative effect on the productivity of innovative informal firms, those firms that remain informal but that were able to introduce *radical* or *soft* innovations exhibit greater labor productivity than firms that start their activity in the formal sector.

Thus, these could necessitate additional policies that support informal firms to reallocate their resources and invest both in R&D and employee training. While some policies - such as simplifying registration procedures and reducing associated costs - can encourage to informal firms transition into formal ones, they may not be enough to enhance the productivity of informal firms. Indeed, our study reveals that, when they reallocate resources to R&D, innovative informal firms could be also more productive than formal ones.

Given our robust empirical evidence, we suggest policies that address the specific challenges of informal enterprises. For instance, these policies may encourage innovative behavior of informal firms, preserving their high degree of flexibility and adaptability. Since informal firms have close relationships with their local customer, this proximity provides valuable insights into customer preferences, enabling them to introduce product improvements that are better suited to the needs of the local target market. Then, they are usually also more responsive to changes in the market than formal firms. On the other hand, their lower costs could also allow them to intro-

duce innovations with less effort. Nevertheless, since informal firms face lower entry costs than formal firms, the fiercer competition of informal firms could shrink the incentives for formal firms to invest in innovative activities.

Therefore, policymakers should look to reforms that balance the need for the integration of informal enterprises into the formal sector while the preserving the lean, flexible, and adaptable characteristics typically associated with informal enterprises. At the same time, such policies should take into account any adverse effects on the firms' productivity in the formal sector. By doing so, such policies could have the chance to boost innovation, improve productivity, and drive the whole economic growth in emerging countries.

6. CONCLUSIONS

It is crucial to gain a deeper understanding of the impact of innovation on firms' performances in emerging countries. Informal firms in these countries, which employ a significant portion of the population, face challenges due to their low productivity and inefficiency, as well as socio-economic and political obstacles that limit their access to resources and knowledge. In this challenging environment, innovation could be a key factor for their survival and increased productivity.

Nevertheless, informal firms can play a significant role in terms of innovations. Informal firms are often more flexible and responsive to changes in the market than formal firms. Hence, they may quickly introduce new products or improve the existing ones. Informal firms also have a close relationship with their customers. It grants them valuable insights into their needs and preferences and can lead to product improvements that are better suited to the needs of the local target market. Moreover, since informal firms are often able to operate at lower costs than formal firms, they may introduce innovations with fewer efforts. Therefore, policy-makers should be aware that innovation is not just a result of economic growth but rather a tool for development. Especially in the informal economy, innovations are often overlooked

and not adequately supported. Thus, innovative policies that address financial and labor skills obstacles and incentivize R&D expenditures are crucial for long-run growth and for enhancing catch-up with developed countries. As such, it is fundamental to acknowledge the critical role that R&D, innovations, and knowledge may play in transforming the economy and promoting development.

While some policy actions, such as easing the registration process or related costs, may transform informal firms into formal ones, they could not be sufficient to foster their productivity. In this context, our paper suggests deploying additional policies supporting informal firms to reallocate their resources and invest in R&D and employee training. Hence, since our study found successful innovative informal Vietnamese firms more productive than formal ones, policies should encourage the transition to the formal economy, but they should also retain their high level of flexibility. In this way, such policies could enhance firms' innovation, increase their productivity, and drive economic progress in emerging economies.

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